

DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF THERMOSPLASTIC/CARBON FIBER PREPREGS AND COMPOSITES

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Carbon fiber yarns have been impregnated with molten nylon 6,6 and polyester thermoplastics following which they were drum wound to form prepreg sheets. A series of fiber finishes were screened for each polymer and the optimum selected for extensive composite evaluation. Following the screening, larger unidirectional and quasi-isotropic laminates were prepared for flexural, shear and tensile strength evaluation. The effects of temperature, moisture and solvents have been evaluated for both systems. A developmental prepreg tape has been prepared with multiple yarns and polyester thermoplastic. Initial composite evaluations of this tape are reported.

INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic matrix resins have significant potential for reducing the cost of composite structures. Several studies [1-3] have demonstrated cost savings from 25% to 80% over conventional composites and from 20% to 50% over aluminum aircraft structure. These savings are a result of novel manufacturing techniques such as quick consolidation, hot stamping, and rapid joining.

However, the majority of the early work was based on a polysulfone matrix, which unfortunately, does not lend itself to solvent-free prepregging. In addition, polysulfone has extremely poor resistance to fuels, oils, and hydraulic fluids.

In 1976, the potential cost advantages of structural reinforced thermoplastics were recognized by Ford, and the Stanford Research Institute (SRI) was commissioned to develop carbon fiber/thermoplastic materials and processes tailored for automotive applications [4]. This program was later expanded by Celanese and, during 1979, two attractive matrix systems were identified for such applications. These resins are nylon 6,6 and Celanex[®] PBT (polybutylene terephthalate), and both were supplied by Celanese for the program. Celanese also supplied the Celion[®] high strength carbon fiber used in the material and process development.

This presentation reports on the following activities which were involved in the material development and evaluation:

- Screening fiber finishes and identification of optimums.
- Development and optimization of impregnation techniques.
- Development of panel fabrication processes.
- Mechanical property evaluations.
- Thermal, environmental and solvent resistance characterizations.
- Scale-up from single yarn coating to direct prepreg tape preparation.

OPTIMAL FIBER SIZE SELECTION

The fiber used in all of the following evaluations was Celion[®] 6000 carbon fiber, marketed by the Celanese Corporation. The material is a 6000 filament untwisted yarn with the physical and mechanical properties given in Table 1; this is a typical high strength carbon fiber reinforcement product. The starting material contained no finish or sizing (which is necessary for optimal handling). Several finishes were applied to the fiber in the initial evaluations in order to identify and select an optimum finish which would maximize the composite mechanical properties. In addition to ease of handling, proper finishes can and do provide improved wetting and/or adhesion with the matrix resin.

Among the materials evaluated as finishes were various thermoplastic and thermosetting monomers. These included standard epoxy resins, polyamides, polyimides, phenolics, and polyethers. The effects of various finishes were pronounced with the polyester matrix, but the variants appeared to have minimal influence on nylon composite mechanical properties. These results are summarized in Table 2, where the range of results is reviewed but actual finish identifications are coded for proprietary reasons.

The initial evaluations were carried out on small quantities of prepreg made by melt coating at SRI to provide the necessary specimens for screening (see Fig. 1). Prepregging was performed at 1.5 m/min. (5 ft./min.). A small orifice was used at the bath exit in order to limit the resin pick-up to the desired range.

A two-stage molding procedure was used to prepare small laminates for the finish evaluations. In the first stage, the required number of impregnated yarns were wrapped in porous Armalon (Teflon coated glass fabric) to prevent lateral movement. Pre-consolidated blanks were formed by pressing (at very low pressure) the PBT prepregs at 522°K (480°F) and the nylon material at 536°K (505°F) for five minutes. In the second stage laminate formation, the blanks were again wrapped in Armalon to prevent transverse movement, and the PBT and nylon laminates were molded under 0.34 MPa (50 psi) pressure using stops at 522°K (480°F) and 550°K (530°F), respectively.

As indicated in Table 2, finish-type C was selected for use with PBT resin; this variant delivered the highest shear strength along with a good flex strength. The finish selected for further development of the nylon composites was type F. This variant delivered the best balance of shear and flex strengths with the exception of the unsized control which is equivalent in performance. As indicated earlier, selection of the variant with finish was necessary to provide handling ease.

MECHANICAL PROPERTY MEASUREMENT

The mechanical property testing used in the size selection was limited to measurement of short beam shear and flexural strengths at 4:1 and 32:1 span-to-depth ratios, respectively. The tests were carried out in compliance with ASTM Methods D-2344 for shear and D-790 for flexure. For the more complete evaluations which include tension testing, 12.7 mm (1/2") wide tabbed specimens in accordance with ASTM D-3039 were tested. Tensile strain was measured with a two-inch extensometer. Flexural strains were measured using cross-head deflection of the Instron test machines.

FABRICATION PROCEDURES

Celion/PBT Composites

The prepregs, as made in the coating operation, contained in the range of 50 weight percent resin. Because of the resin in excess of the desired level in the finished laminate, it was necessary to incorporate a method to reduce the resin content and the bulk of the prepreg. Bleeder plies accompanied with the following procedure were employed.

Sheets of prepreg 0.14 m x 0.21 m (5½" x 8¼") were made by winding the coated yarns onto a large drum in adjacent parallel fashion and sealing them together into a sheet by using a heated iron. The sheets so prepared were cut to the appropriate dimensions and stacked to provide the desired thickness. Seven plies were used to prepare tension-test laminates; nine plies were used for the flex and shear laminates; and eight plies for the pseudo-isotropic panels. Once again, the lay-ups were wrapped in porous Armalon to prevent lateral fiber movement and to allow bleeding. Two layers of 181 glass cloth were used as bleeder on each surface to absorb the excess resin. The blanks were then pressed between release-coated steel caul plates. To form the blanks, the press and cauls were heated to 522°K (480°F) and the press was closed using 0.34 MPa (50 psi) pressure. Shims were used to guarantee even closure of the press but were removed to allow full application of the pressure. The assembly was held at 522°K (480°F) and 0.34 MPa (50 psi) for five minutes and then cooled. The impregnated bleeder plies were removed and replaced with a single ply of fresh glass fabric on each surface.

For the second-stage pressing, which was the final lamination step, the press and cauls were heated to 536°K (505°F), and 0.34 MPa (50 psi) pressure was applied. After five minutes at this temperature and pressure, the formed laminate was cooled to 422°K (300°F) and removed from the press. The average per ply thickness of the laminates prepared was approximately 0.18 mm. (.007 in.).

Celion/Nylon 66 Composites

The average resin content of the nylon prepreg sheets manufactured by the technique described for PBT was 55 weight percent. Again, the excess resin necessitated a two-stage process similar to that described in the preceding paragraphs. As before, the 0.14 m x 0.21 m (5½" x 8¼") sheets were stacked into seven, eight and nine ply assemblies to provide tensile, flex and shear, and quasi-isotropic specimens, respectively. The first of the two stages, pre-consolidation into a blank using two plies of 181 glass bleeder on each face, was carried out by applying 0.34 MPa (50 psi) at 536°K (505°F) for five (5) minutes. The second stage lamination was carried out at 550°K (530°F) and 0.34 MPa (50 psi), again using a five minute dwell. The laminates were cooled under pressure to 422°K (300°F). The average per ply thickness of the nylon laminates was approximately 0.2 mm (8 mil).

COMPOSITE EVALUATION

Both the nylon 66 and the PBT laminates contained a nominal 60 volume percent fiber based on the material balance of the incorporated materials. Limited ultrasonic C-scan evaluations showed the laminates to be reasonably clear and of good quality. On this basis, an extended mechanical property data base was generated on these materials. This included tensile, flex, and shear strength determinations at ambient conditions, both hot-dry and hot-wet and also after exposure to hot brake and anti-freeze fluids. (The brake fluid used was Prestone Heavy Duty, DOT #3 and the anti-freeze was a 50/50 volume mixture of ethylene glycol and water). The flex and shear strengths of both nylon 66 and PBT composites under both hot-dry and hot-wet conditions are compared in Table 3. It is clear that the wet flex strength of the PBT laminates is superior to the nylon performance; however, the wet nylon shear strengths are surprisingly good and even surpass the corresponding wet PBT properties. These superior nylon shear strengths indicate better fiber wetting plus adhesion and/or less critical residual stresses at the fiber-matrix interface. The remaining properties obtained on the two resin systems are discussed separately as follows:

Celion/PBT Performance

The Celion/PBT mechanical property performance is summarized in Tables 4 through 7. Tables 4 and 5 detail the flex and shear and the tensile strengths, respectively, for the unidirectional composites. The flex, shear and tensile strengths are not seriously affected by temperature exposure, but they are reduced by 10 to 20% after both hot moisture and hot anti-freeze conditioning. The brake fluid causes the specimens to disintegrate during 24 hour exposure at >473°K (400°F). Similar responses were seen with the quasi-isotropic laminates in tensile, flex and shear tests (see Tables 6 and 7). The tensile strengths are very well maintained. In contrast, the quasi-isotropic shear strengths are quite low, even for the control tested at ambient. This casts some suspicion on the quality of these laminates and evaluations, which include microscopy and resin digestion, are underway.

As can be seen in Table 7, the quasi-isotropic laminate tensile strength is not affected by a 24 hour exposure to brake fluid. The target soak temperature during the other PBT brake fluid exposures went above 400°F and was not in control. Insufficient material remained to repeat the tests at the proper temperature at the time of the initial characterization. However, this will be carried out in the near future.

Celion/Nylon 66 Performance

The Celion/nylon mechanical properties are summarized in Tables 8 and 9, with unidirectional flex and shear shown in Table 8 and tensile properties shown in Table 9. The flex strengths for nylon are comparable to those of PBT composites, except for the moisture and anti-freeze aged specimens, while the nylon

shear strengths are all quite superior. The nylon tensile strengths are at least equivalent to those obtained with PBT resin except for the moisture conditioned sets, where the PBT is 10% greater, and the anti-freeze and brake fluid conditioned specimens where nylon is clearly superior.

In comparing nylon to PBT carbon fiber reinforced laminates, it appears that the nylon composites are superior in most aspects, in particular with respect to short beam shear strength. However, the PBT laminates show better flex and tensile strengths following hot-wet conditioning than the corresponding nylon laminates. This is not surprising in light of the known plasticizing effects of moisture on nylon thermoplastics. It also appears that PBT resistance to anti-freeze may be superior to nylon performance.

PREPREG STABILITY

Two characteristics of prepregs which are of great interest to molders are their RT shelf life and their moisture sensitivity. The matrix most likely to be affected by these parameters is the nylon 66 polymer. For this reason, the impact of these variables on Celion/nylon prepreg performance has been evaluated. Table 12 shows the results of shelf life (e.g., 48 days at ambient) on nylon/Celion composite shear strength. As can be seen, there is some decrease after long out times; but the shear strength can be significantly recovered by pre-drying the prepreg prior to fabrication.

In a separate experiment, the effect of moisturization of nylon resin prior to impregnation on flex and shear strength has been evaluated. The results of this study are shown in Table 13. It is clear that moisturized nylon impregnates the fiber better than the dry counterpart and laminates with superior flex and shear strengths result from final laminate fabrication. Presumably the property improvement is due to moisture plasticization of the matrix resulting in improved flow and wetting during the coating operation. This highlights the importance of good wetting during impregnation on final composite quality and performance.

CONTINUING DEVELOPMENT

The results discussed thus far have been obtained on composite laminates formed from sheets wound after melt coating single yarns of Celion carbon fiber with nylon or PBT. It is quite apparent that this does not constitute a commercial process. The prepreg preparation has been tedious and the molding times are far from commercial in that total spans of 30 to 60 minutes have been involved.

To alleviate these constraints, current efforts are underway to form sheets by simultaneously coating multiple carbon fiber yarns. In order to carry out this process, proprietary dies have been manufactured which allow crosshead extrusion coating to form impregnated tapes. These tapes have been used to extend the evaluations discussed above.

Composite laminate test specimens have been formed by hot pressing the tapes at 522°K (480°F) to 550°K (530°F), respectively, for PBT and nylon. In addition to flex and tensile strengths, moduli are also being measured along with exact fiber loading using resin digestion techniques. Formic acid digestion is being used for the nylon laminate while trifluoroacetic acid digestion is used for PBT. The data generated in the preliminary stages are show in Table 14. It is clear that fiber property translation is better than indicated by the earlier measurements. Correction of strengths and moduli to 62 volume percent (a common range for thermoset composites) shows tensile strengths and moduli in the 1520 MPa (220 x 10³) and 138 GPa (20 x 10⁶ psi) ranges, respectively. These properties are only marginally lower than those observed with standard thermoset composites.

In the continuing development program, more extensive property measurements are underway. Specifically, transverse tensile and flex, as well as compression properties, are being measured. The relatively low T_g 's of the current matrix materials are expected to limit applications. To enable the use of thermoplastic carbon fiber reinforced materials in more strenuous conditions, more durable matrix materials are being sought. Evaluation of such matrices and their carbon fiber composites is currently underway.

REFERENCES

- 1 MAXIMOVICH, M.G., National SAMPE Conference Series, 19, 262, 1974.
- 2 HOGGATT, J.T., National SAMPE Conference Series, 20, 606, 1975.
- 3 MAY, C.L. and GOAD, R. AFML-TR-75-111, 1976.
- 4 Ford Motor Company Research Agreement, No. 47-2-532538 (SRI International Project 6218).

Fig. 1 Schematic of Hot Melt Prepreg Preparation

	<u>SI Units</u>	<u>English Units</u>
<u>Fiber Properties</u>		
Tensile Strength*	3100 MPa	450x10 ³ psi
Tensile Modulus*	234 GPa	34x10 ⁶ psi
Ultimate Elongation*	1.3%	1.3%
Density	1.77 g/cm ³	0.064 lb/in ³
Electrical Resistivity	1500 $\mu\Omega$ -cm	9000 Ω -mil-ft

Yarn-Tow Characteristics

Filament Diameter	7.1x10 ⁻⁶ m	0.28x10 ⁻³ in
Filament Shape	Round	Round
Filament Count	6000	6000
Fiber Area in Yarn		
Cross Section	0.24 mm ²	3.6x10 ⁻⁴ in ²
Yield	0.411 g/m	1208 yd/lb
Twist	None	None
Size Level	1.1%	1.1%

*Impregnated Strand Test Method

TABLE 1

TYPICAL CELION[®] CARBON FIBER PROPERTIES

<u>A. PBT POLYESTER</u>					
<u>Finish Type</u>	<u>Flex Strength</u>		<u>Short Beam Shear Strength</u>		
	<u>MPa</u>	<u>(10³ psi)</u>	<u>MPa</u>	<u>(10³ psi)</u>	
None	920	(133)	34.5	(5.0)	
A	900	(131)	42.7	(6.2)	
B	1250	(182)	62.7	(9.1)	
C*	1250	(181)	68.2	(9.9)	
D	1160	(168)	61.3	(8.9)	

*Selected for further studies.

<u>B. NYLON 66</u>					
<u>Finish Type</u>	<u>Flex Strength</u>		<u>Short Beam Shear Strength</u>		
	<u>MPa</u>	<u>(10³ psi)</u>	<u>MPa</u>	<u>(10³ psi)</u>	
None	1270	(185)	94.4	(13.7)	
B	1140	(166)	93.7	(13.6)	
E	1270	(184)	86.8	(12.6)	
F*	1230	(179)	94.4	(13.7)	
G	1330	(193)	78.5	(11.4)	

*Selected for further studies

TABLE 2

EFFECT OF FINISH ON CELION[®]
6000/THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE PERFORMANCE

Sample	Condition	Test		Short Beam	
		Temperature °K (°F)	Flex Strength MPa (10 ³ .psi)	Shear Strength MPa (10 ³ psi)	
Celion/Polyester ¹	Dry	295 (72)	1160 (168)	64.8 (9.4)	
Celion/Polyester ¹	Dry	355 (180)	760 (110)	40.7 (5.9)	
Celion/Polyester ¹	Dry	394 (250)	530 (77)	35.1 (5.1)	
Celion/Polyester ¹	Wet ²	295 (72)	1140 (166)	44.8 (6.5)	
Celion/Polyester ¹	Wet ²	355 (180)	680 (98)	33.8 (4.9)	
Celion/Nylon ³	Dry	295 (72)	1250 (181)	84.1 (12.2)	
Celion/Nylon ³	Dry	355 (180)	720 (105)	73.0 (10.6)	
Celion/Nylon ³	Dry	394 (250)	610 (89)	66.8 (9.7)	
Celion/Nylon ³	Wet ²	295 (72)	680 (99)	68.9 (10.0)	
Celion/Nylon ³	Wet ²	355 (180)	520 (75)	52.4 (7.6)	

- (1) Finish Type "C"
(2) Saturated at 344°K (160°F)/95% relative humidity
(3) Finish Type "F"

TABLE 3
COMPARATIVE HOT-WET PERFORMANCE OF UNIDIRECTIONAL
CELION THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

TEST TYPE	Flexural Strength		Short Beam Shear Strength	
	295 (72)	355 (180)	295 (72)	355 (180)
TEST TEMPERATURE, °K(°F)	MPa (10 ³ psi)			
UNITS				
<u>CONTROL</u>	1250 (181)	710 (103)	58.6 (8.5)	44.1 (6.4)
<u>MOISTURE AGED</u> 344°K(160°F)/95% R.H.	1140 (166)	680 (98)	44.8 (6.5)	33.8 (4.9)
<u>HEAT AGED IN AIR</u> 24 H. at 355°K (180°F)	1230 (178)	760 (110)	60.6 (8.8)	40.7 (5.9)
<u>ANTI-FREEZE</u> 24 H. at 383°K (230°F)	1140 (165)		53.7 (7.8)	
<u>BRAKE FLUID</u> 24 H. at 473°K (400°F)				
	-----DISINTEGRATES-----			

TABLE 4
FLEX AND SHEAR STRENGTHS OF
UNIDIRECTIONAL CELION/PBT COMPOSITES

TEST TEMPERATURE, °K(0°F)	295 (72)	355 (180)	394 (250)
UNITS	MPa (10 ³ psi)	MPa (10 ³ psi)	MPa (10 ³ psi)
CONTROL	1140 (165)	960 (139)	
<u>MOISTURE AGED</u>			
344°K(160°F)/95% R.H.	900 (131)	680 (98)	
<u>HEAT AGED IN AIR</u>			
24 H. at 355°K(180°F)	1100 (160)	990 (143)	
24 H. at 394°K(250°F)	1170 (170)		880 (127)
<u>ANTI-FREEZE</u>			
24 H. at 383°K(230°F)	930 (135)		
<u>BRAKE FLUID</u>			
24 H. at 473°K(400°F)			

-----DISINTEGRATES-----

TABLE 5

TENSILE STRENGTHS OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CELION/PBT COMPOSITES

TEST TYPE	Flexural Strength		Short Beam Shear Strength	
	295 (72)	355 (180)	295 (72)	355 (180)
TEST TEMPERATURE, °K(0°F)				
UNITS	MPa(10 ³ psi)	MPa(10 ³ psi)	MPa(10 ³ psi)	MPa(10 ³ psi)
CONTROL	500 (73)	340 (49)	27.6 (4.0)	25.5 (3.7)
<u>MOISTURE AGED</u>				
344°K(160°F)/95% R.H.	430 (62)	310 (45)	19.3 (2.8)	15.2 (2.2)
<u>HEAT AGED IN AIR</u>				
24 H. at 355°K(180°F)	480 (70)	360 (52)	28.2 (4.1)	22.7 (3.3)
<u>ANTI-FREEZE</u>				
24 H. at 383°K(230°F)	440 (64)		22.0 (3.2)	
<u>BRAKE FLUID</u>				
24 H. at 473°K(400°F)				

-----DISINTEGRATES-----

TABLE 6

FLEX AND SHEAR STRENGTHS OF QUASI-ISOTROPIC CELION/PBT COMPOSITES

TEST TEMPERATURE, °K(0°F)	295 (72)	355 (180)	394 (250)
UNITS	MPa (10 ³ psi)	MPa (10 ³ psi)	MPa (10 ³ psi)
CONTROL	230 (34)	200 (29)	
<u>MOISTURE AGED</u>			
344°K(160°F)/95% R.H.	190 (28)	160 (23)	
<u>HEAT AGED</u>			
24 H. at 355°K(180°F)	220 (32)	210 (31)	
24 H. at 394°K(250°F)	230 (33)		260 (38)
<u>ANTI-FREEZE</u>			
24 H. at 383°K(230°F)	200 (29)		
<u>BRAKE FLUID</u>			
24 H. at 394°K(250°F)	230 (33)		

TABLE 7

TENSILE STRENGTHS OF QUASI-ISOTROPIC CELION/PBT COMPOSITES

TEST TYPE	Flexural Strength		Short Beam Shear Strength	
	295 (72)	355 (180)	295 (72)	355 (180)
TEST TEMPERATURE, °K(0°F)				
UNITS	MPa(10 ³ psi)	MPa(10 ³ psi)	MPa(10 ³ psi)	MPa(10 ³ psi)
CONTROL	1230 (179)	690 (100)	94.4 (13.7)	59.9 (8.7)
MOISTURE AGED 344°K(160°F)/95% R.H.	680 (99)	520 (75)	68.9 (10.0)	52.4 (7.6)
HEAT AGED IN AIR 24 H. at 355°K (180°F)	1190 (173)	720 (105)	93.7 (13.6)	73.0 (10.6)
ANTI-FREEZE 24 H. at 383°K (230°F)	670 (97)		69.6 (10.1)	
BRAKE FLUID 24 H. at 413°K (284°F)	760 (110)		56.5 (8.2)	

TABLE 8

FLEX AND SHEAR STRENGTHS OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CELION/NYLON COMPOSITES

TEST TEMPERATURE, °K(0°F)	295 (72)	355 (180)	394 (250)
UNITS	MPa (10 ³ psi)	MPa (10 ³ psi)	MPa (10 ³ psi)
CONTROL	1220 (177)	940 (136)	
MOISTURE AGED 344°K(160°F)/95% R.H.	810 (117)	800 (116)	
HEAT AGED IN AIR 24 H. at 355°K(180°F)	1140 (166)	1060 (154)	
24 H. at 394°K(250°F)	1180 (171)		1000 (145)
ANTI-FREEZE 24 H. at 383°K(230°F)	1070 (155)		
BRAKE FLUID 24 H. at 413°K(284°F)	1280 (186)		

TABLE 9

TENSILE STRENGTHS OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CELION/NYLON COMPOSITES

TEST TYPE	Flexural Strength		Short Beam Shear Strength	
	295 (72)	355 (180)	295 (72)	355 (180)
TEST TEMPERATURE, °K(0°F)				
UNITS	MPa(10 ³ psi)	MPa(10 ³ psi)	MPa(10 ³ psi)	MPa(10 ³ psi)
CONTROL	700 (101)	450 (66)	65.5 (9.5)	48.9 (7.1)
MOISTURE AGED 344°K(160°F)/95% R.H.	500 (72)	390 (57)	53.1 (7.7)	41.3 (6.0)
HEAT AGED IN AIR 24 H. at 355°K (180°F)	720 (105)	500 (73)	64.1 (9.3)	56.5 (8.2)
ANTI-FREEZE 24 H. at 383°K (230°F)	500 (73)		53.7 (7.8)	
BRAKE FLUID 24 H. at 413°K (284°F)	440 (64)		29.6 (4.3)	

TABLE 10

FLEX AND SHEAR STRENGTHS OF QUASI-ISOTROPIC CELION/NYLON COMPOSITES

TEST TEMPERATURE, °K(0°F)	295	(72)	355	(180)	394	(250)
UNITS	MPa	(10 ³ psi)	MPa	(10 ³ psi)	MPa	(10 ³ psi)
CONTROL	400	(58)	289	(42)		
MOISTURE AGED						
344°K(160°F)/95% R.H.	340	(49)	310	(45)		
HEAT AGED IN AIR						
24 H. at 355°K(180°F)	430	(62)	340	(50)		
24 H. at 394°K(250°F)	430	(62)			370	(54)
ANTI-FREEZE						
24 H. at 383°K(230°F)	350	(51)				
BRAKE FLUID						
24 H. at 413°K(284°F)	440	(64)				

TABLE 11

TENSILE STRENGTHS OF QUASI-ISOTROPIC CELION/NYLON COMPOSITES

Nylon/Celion 6000	Prepreg Shelf Life	Short-Beam Shear Strength		Change in Value From Control (%)
		MPa	(10 ³ psi)	
Original	0	79.2	(11.5)	Control
Molding No. 1	48 days	62.0	(9.0)	-21.8
Molding No. 2	48 days + 3 hr @ 215 F	70.3	(10.2)	-11.1

TABLE 12

RESULTS OF SHELF-LIFE STUDY

Type of Composite	Short Beam Shear Strength Matrix			Flexural Strength Matrix	
	Moisturized for 96 H.	Pre-Dried Matrix	MPa (10 ³ psi)	Moisturized for 96 H.	Pre-Dried Matrix
				MPa (10 ³ psi)	MPa (10 ³ psi)
Celion/Nylon	93.7 (13.6)	84.1 (12.2)		1270 (185)	1250 (181)
Celion/PBT	48.9 (7.1)	43.4 (6.3)		1230 (179)	1070 (155)

TABLE 13

MOISTURE EFFECT BEFORE IMPREGNATION

	Flex Strength		Modulus	
	MPa (10 ³ psi)	(10 ³ psi)	GPa (10 ⁶ psi)	(10 ⁶ psi)
Celion/Nylon	1570	(228)	127	(18.4)
Celion/PBT	1260	(183)	142	(20.6)

TABLE 14

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CELION LAMINATES

MADE FROM THERMOPLASTIC TAPES